

Phase 3: Quantified Policy Package & Knowledge Exchange

We collated the evidence and lessons learned from Phase 1 and Phase 2 to create a quantified, bespoke, citizen-led and citizen-inclusive policy packet for each city. This entailed we:

Knowledge exchange

Gathered transferable lessons and steps for better practice based on the experiences of the ClairCity project; and made the lessons learnt known to other stakeholders.

Impact Assessment

Rapidly quantified the effects of the final UPS.

Policy package

Summarised the findings and delivered the political possibilities and effects of these possibilities to each city.

The result...

For a future with clean air

Our PARTNER CITIES:

Get in touch if this would work well for your city!

claircity.eu

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The ClairCity Methodology

For citizen inclusive decision-making

Our future with clean air
www.claircity.eu

ClairCity

Citizens engagement drives policy

ClairCity aimed to:

- raise awareness about air pollution and carbon emissions in our cities and to improve policy making
- look at how our behaviour contributes to the problems and affects the air we breathe
- put the power in the hands of residents to determine the best local solutions.

To achieve these aims, the ClairCity method was divided into three phases listed below. This iterative approach allowed citizens to draw upon a solid evidence base, understand issues more deeply and make decisions based on the evidence.

Phase 1: Today's situation

To understand the local context and establish a baseline of citizens behaviours for modelling we:

Benchmarking behaviour

Understood and quantified the baseline status of air quality, carbon emissions and related public health in our cities.

Assessment of policy

Quantified current air quality emissions concentrations, carbon emissions and public health impacts in each city.

Quantify the baseline

Analysed current policies (local, regional, national and EU) that influenced each city.

Phase 2: Engagement and co-creation with citizens and stakeholders

Phase two aimed to:

- Raise awareness of the environmental challenges and their solutions
- Understand citizens' current behaviours, practices and activities
- Enable citizens and stakeholders to co-create and visualise their future city

Public engagement and awareness

To creatively engage citizens in each city we:

Community films

Engaged older people, a more vulnerable group, to talk about the changes in their city, their personal mobility and the steps they take to minimise their exposure.

The GreenAnt app

Allowed citizens to become citizen scientists and monitor their transport activities, emission generation and exposure using mobile GPS data.

City Events

Provided healthy and smart tips to promote non-motorised mobility of citizens by highlighting availability and benefits of walking and cycling routes in the city.

Schools Engagement: My City, School, & Home

Engaged young people in the air quality, carbon and public health debate. Utilise an online platform for students to be able to design tools for change towards smart consumption, reduced emissions and healthy lifestyles.

Citizen and Stakeholder Engagement & Co-creation of Scenarios

To enable citizen-led air pollution reduction we:

Delphi Method

A) Called upon the expertise of citizens to generate qualitative evidence. This highlighted their entrenched behaviours and what enabling interventions could allow them to act and behave differently in the future.

ClairCity Skylines Game

B) 'Crowd-sourced' public perceptions and public acceptability of different policy interventions.

Mutual Learning Workshop

C) Brought citizens and stakeholders together to debate the challenges facing the city and co-created policy interventions for cleaner, healthier futures.

Stakeholder dialogue

Brought citizens and stakeholders together to review and debate the proposed measures and co-created scenarios for a low carbon, clean air, healthy future relevant to that city.

Policy workshop

Transformed the scenarios into workable policies before returning to local citizens to discuss and agree on a single Unified Policy Scenario (UPS).

